

the ECS Collaboration Group digital magazine

Citizen Science Lighthouse

Special edition #2023

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Editorial

Our Citizen Science Lighthouse

Simona Cerrato, ECS and ECSA communication manager

December 2023

Image credits: Simona Cerrato

Four key themes are explored through in-depth analyses in this special issue of the Citizen Science Lighthouse, the digital magazine of the European Citizen Science (ECS) project. We discuss how to recruit, motivate, and engage participants in citizen science initiatives, explore how to measure impact, reflect on how to share results with citizens and society at large, delve into legal challenges, and examine the relationship between the law and citizen science. The authors of these reflections are experts in their fields and actively work on citizen science in various capacities. These reflections are the result of discussions held in the ECS Collaboration Group organised monthly throughout 2023.

The title of our magazine is not coincidental; it fits into a metaphor we adopted at the beginning of the project to express its complexity and richness of perspectives, ideas, and experiences. ECS is like an archipelago within a vast ocean, with the latter representing the realm of citizen science. The islands, referring to the platform, academy, media, communities, news and events, and resources, belong to the same system, yet each one has its own specific characteristics. Beyond the borders of the archipelago extends the great ocean of citizen science open to exploration and new knowledge. On the [eu-citizen.science platform](https://eu-citizen.science), sailors (citizen science

practitioners, citizen scientists, the general public, researchers, educators, policy makers, funding bodies, decision makers, the press, etc.) will find the map of the archipelago: access to all available resources and opportunities to connect with the community.

This metaphor vividly depicts our work for the four years of the project and beyond: the sharing of knowledge through the platform and the ECS Academy, collaboration between different stakeholders, the exchange of experiences, the production and re-use of relevant tools, the organisation of local and international events, and a strategy for policy engagement and co-designing policy recommendations, among others. These reflections, guided by the lighthouse's light, should help find a safe route to navigate through the vast ocean of citizen science. The ECS project is strongly based on the participation of the entire community and co-creation. This editorial is also an invitation to join our effort to mainstream citizen science, contributing to the democratisation of science and research.

And finally, an invitation to follow us: subscribe to our [digital magazine](#), explore the [eu-citizen.science platform](#), and follow us on social media.

Our social media	
Facebook	@EUCitSciProject
Instagram	@EU-Citizen.Science
Twitter	@EUCitSciProject

The ECS project at a glance

ecs
european citizen science

Goal
Widening and strengthening the European citizen science community through capacity building and awareness is the main goal of the **European Citizen Science (ECS)** project.

Vision
A globally connected, **inclusive and strong citizen science community** for societal change in Europe.

The European Citizen Science 5Cs mission

- Capacity building and training services
- Common platform uniting diverse European actors
- Creating and sharing of citizen science data and knowledge
- Contributing to European policy making
- Changing today's societal challenges into future opportunities through citizen science

At a glance

What ECS does

1. Expanding the **reach of citizen science** by strengthening the **community**
2. Enhancing **digital skills** for **FAIR** and **open science** communities
3. Further **developing the Eu-Citizen.Science platform** through co-design
4. Developing the **ECS academy** with **free training** to increase the capacity to conduct citizen science
5. Boosting **inclusion and diversity** for mainstreaming citizen science
6. **Advocating** for citizen science and working on **policy impacts**
7. Investigating the **impact** of citizen science on **research, society and economy**

What you can do

1. Explore the **European Citizen Science platform** and discover training **courses, resources, stories, videos, events.** eu-citizen.science
2. Register and **be part of the community:** promote your organisation, projects, events
3. Take part in the **co-design** sessions
4. Take part in the **forum discussions**
5. Contribute to **build the citizen science community**
6. Take part in the **community events**
7. **Learn** about citizen science **projects** in Europe

Countries **15** Citizen science ambassadors **28**

Affiliated entities **9** Years from August 2022 to July 2026 **4**

Partners **12** ~ Million euros budget **4**

ecsa European Citizen Science Association
Coordination

To know more

eu-citizenscienceproject

eu-citizen.science

Funded by the European Union

Partners: CSIC, ecsa, ibericivis, NORDECO, NILU, etc.

Affiliated entities: MUSEO, UGN, etc.

Citizen science for social transformation: measuring the impact of citizen science initiatives

Stefanie Schürz, Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (Austria)

June 2023

Image credits: Ars Electronica, Linz , Austria(Ph: Simona Cerrato)

While impact assessment remains a complex issue, a lot of experience and expertise has already been developed within the citizen science community of practice on how to approach and implement impact assessment in a holistic manner – taking into account the needs and expectations of citizen scientists, professional scientists, wider stakeholder communities, funding agencies, and policymakers. Progress has been made in elevating the profile of citizen generated data for policy making, while new impact metrics are being considered on all levels of the R&I system. Still,

tensions arise when different impact logics meet. While these must be met in contextually sensitive ways, ethical principles cannot be neglected just to fulfil performance metrics – which might ultimately be harmful not just to engaged citizen communities, but wider society.

We explored this theme during the first thematic meeting of the ECS collaboration group and we now share the different perspectives addressed on: 1. How to measure the positive influence on society and social groups? 2. How to convince public

authorities that citizen science data are good for policy decisions? 3. How to initiate the potential for social impact? 4. How to use labels in CS in ethical appropriate ways?. It is a step on a long journey to continue reflection in the community.

How we worked

The first thematic session of the ECS Collaboration Group meeting was held on March 7, 2023 with a focus on the evaluation and impact assessment of citizen science initiatives. The session was prepared and hosted by Stefanie Schürz, Teresa Schäfer and Barbara Kieslinger (ZSI/ECS project), with support from Antonella Passani (IMPETUS), Usue Lorenz (YouCount) and Stephen Parkinson (MICS).

In preparation of the session, the hosts sent out a grid to be filled by the members of the group, outlining their most important impacts and the challenges they faced in achieving them. From these inputs, ZSI developed four recurring of a limited, short-term project. While outcomes are still within the scope of such interventions, larger impacts on e.g. the environment, behaviour, or policymaking usually unfold over time and are sometimes hard to quantify. Especially more abstract impacts such as raising awareness of an issue, science literacy, community building, or empowerment are not easily measured in a standardised, quantifiable manner. Some impacts might also be small and hard to scale, like direct impact on the participating citizens, and it might not be clear how these impacts affect wider society. The group suggested looking outside the scope of singular projects and towards the combined efforts of a plethora of thematically and methodologically related initiatives on various geographic scales – from the regional to the global. This might be a way of both continuing to measure impact beyond the runtime of a project and amplifying the impact achievable by individual, time-limited projects. Finally, dissemination and exploitation were also mentioned as important pillars of longer-term transformation, which ties both into the role of social media outreach and community building, as well as the role of traditional media, which has shown increasing attention to citizen science.

questions and prepared them for discussion in breakout rooms anchored by an interactive Jamboard. The main points of these conversations are summarised below. In total, 29 initiatives and 35 colleagues took part in the exercise.

Figure 1: Jamboard created in Group 1

1. How to measure the positive influence on society and social groups?

In the first group, the main focus of the conversation revolved around the question of how to measure long-term impact within the timeframe

Figure 2: Jamboard created in Group 2

2. How to convince public authorities that citizen science data are good for policy decisions?

In this group, a lot of best practice examples were shared where citizen science produced data was either picked up by, or its value inscribed into policy. For instance, advocacy efforts by ECSA and citizen science initiatives via success stories led to the explicit recognition of citizen science and crowdsourcing as sources of environmental monitoring data in the reworked UNECE Aarhus Convention, namely in the recommendations on electronic information tools¹. Similarly, the

¹ The Aarhus Convention is the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) Convention on access to

European Network of Environmental Protection Agencies set up an Interest Group on Citizen Science (IGCS) to improve the understanding and use of citizen science within environmental policy and governance². Examples from concrete projects collecting data for policy that were shared in the group focus on odour pollution, use of natural resources, biodiversity monitoring, and others. Thus, the field of environmental monitoring gives overall rich evidence of the potential policy impact of citizen science, while showing a number of learnings to observe going forward: First of all, it is important to understand that policymakers need to be made aware of the existence and the strengths of employing citizen generated data. They need to be shown the added value of such data, and their buy-in must be ensured. At the same time, such data must be made accessible to decision makers, and it needs to be translated in such a way that it is useful to both science and policy. This includes not just a contextual understanding of the data, but also data and metadata standards that allow for its use by ministries, agencies, scientists, and statistical offices. To this end, understanding the data and its needs in terms of quality and make-up is key. In each case, the question must be answered in practical terms of how data can be translated between various target groups – citizen scientists, professional scientists, policy makers – and into legislation and policy action. In this context the importance was also pointed to critically reflect on how data and initiatives can be protected from being instrumentalised by any one political party. And, as always, the challenges of securing sufficient resources to create policy impact remains to be considered.

information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice in environmental matters. The updated recommendations on the more effective use of electronic information tools can be found here: https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2022-05/ECE_MPPP_2021_2_Add.2_E.pdf A concrete example of the advocacy efforts undertaken by ECSA can be seen here: https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/pp/a_to_i/7th_meeting/Statements_and_Presentations/7TFAI_IV_4_EITRec_ESCA_Haklay.pdf and here: <https://citizenscience.org/2020/10/07/supporting-environmental-democracy-and-the-aarhus-convention/>

<https://epanet.eea.europa.eu/reports-letters/epa-network-interest-group-on-citizen-science/epa-network-interest-group-on-citizen-science>

Figure 3: Jamboard created in Group 3

3. How to initiate the potential for social impact?

The third group focused their discussion on two questions. First, the group discussed how to successfully deal with awareness raising, recruiting, motivation, behavioural change, and sustainability to initiate the potential for social impact. Regarding the recruitment process, participants touched on the difficulties brought on by the use of digital technologies (webs/apps), which brings up many questions from how to address the digital divide through budgeting of such tools to privacy concerns. A decentralised approach to recruitment via the dissemination through various partner networks was named as beneficial, as was the use of different communication channels/strategies depending on the target group, but also the country of recruitment (e.g., newspapers in Germany, TV in Italy, national radio in France). Schools can also be a target for CS, but there is a need for specific educational materials for this to be successful. The role of established networks, associations and other multiplier organisations was also stressed, although their role also depends on whether citizens are already organised in the region and field of interest, and, associated with this, the already existing levels of mobilisation and motivation. It was also pointed out how it is always somewhat unpredictable how many citizen scientists a recruitment effort will mobilise. Organising regular feedback loops with consortium members about recruitment can be beneficial in adjusting a project's approach. To keep citizen scientists motivated and achieve sustainable change, it can also be beneficial to involve them in dissemination efforts of the project and the results. To keep all involved stakeholders engaged, it is also important to balance the opinions represented in a consortium, including potential differences between lay and scientific

citizens' opinions on certain controversial topics. In any case, being aware and addressing cultural and subcultural differences – including between different countries – is key.

Regarding the question of how to approach different languages in transdisciplinary projects, the group was united in the opinion that native languages work best for successful communication. The citizen science initiatives represented in the group employed translations both produced within the consortium team and by technological means to meet the different stakeholder groups. Some colleagues could draw on good experiences with (private) facebook groups in different languages to support new participants and connect with each other. However, an important caveat is that this is not possible through the app for security reasons.

Figure 4: Jamboard created in Group 4

4. How to use labels in CS in ethical appropriate ways?

The fourth group focused on the question of ethical classification. As certain standards are needed for accurate and comparable measurements, it is important to take into account ethical considerations when choosing labels. This is especially true in cases when marginalised and underserved groups are engaged, where certain labels may be dangerous or reinforce existing inequalities. In the discussion, once consideration brought up was the question of whether people want to identify with certain categories such as old, poor, or disabled, and in turn how to approach possible negative connotations of certain labels. As a solution, it was proposed to use language in appropriate and respectful ways while not disregarding social and material realities. Another potential approach is to let people label themselves, i.e., to let them self-identify. This, however, might be easier done in interactive activities rather than situations where specific

underserved groups are sought out for inclusion. At this step of a process, it might be helpful to draw on specific organisations already serving such communities without having to label participants beyond that. Through this, participants are allowed to take part as individuals rather than representatives of certain societal groups. Furthermore, organisational data might be used instead of forcing people to label themselves, while people are not put into situations where they might be pressured to out themselves.

Finally, it is also important to ask for whom the monitoring and reporting in certain categories is done – namely usually the funders rather than the participants. The pressure to produce Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) might not be compatible with ethical considerations, especially if it tries to make quantifiable the lifeworlds of people without capturing their quality and complexity. KPIs also often come back to what funders expect in terms of outcomes, instead of focusing on the needs and expectations of the engaged communities. Thus, it is important to keep some flexibility in the definition of KPIs and leave space for co-creation and co-definition of project goals. At the same time, the complexity this entails may also be overwhelming, depending at least in part on the employed methodology. In turn, existing and established labels may also be helpful, depending at least in part on the intended audience of an intervention. In any case, it is paramount to respect the contextuality of a project and be clear about its scope and limits. Having more time to reflect and adjust an approach is also always beneficial.

Text and image credit: Stefanie Schürz (bigger formats are available on the [original blog post](#) on the eu.citizen.science platform).

Sharing results with citizens

Anna Sanchez Vidal, David Kocman, Diego Casado-Mansilla and Florence Gignac

August 2023

Drawing from the Sensing for Justice project graphic novel. Credits: Alice Toietta for SensJus

It is a fundamental aspect, which can sometimes turn into a challenge, to share the results with citizens, that is, with anyone who participates and contributes to a citizen science project. So much so that it is underlined by three out of the [10 Principles of citizen science](#).

1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavours that generate new knowledge or understanding. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.

4. Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process. This may

include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.

8. Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.

Many tools available today to develop, implement and evaluate citizen science initiatives address this aspect. For example, the [Action toolkit](#) dedicates considerable attention to sharing and publishing results. And there are many projects currently underway that have useful ideas and contributions.

At their core, the effective sharing of research results plays a pivotal role in cultivating societal trust in the scientific community. To achieve this, it is essential to guide and provide citizens with well-informed resources that enable them to understand and interpret the data.

Customising result sharing to meet participant preferences, expectations and motivations

When it comes to sharing research results, giving careful thought to the preferences and expectations of participants is crucial. Understanding how they intend to utilise the findings from your project allows you to personalise the dissemination process. In the [Cities-Health pilot in Ljubljana](#), they found that while some participants may be interested in downloading the raw data and exploring it on their own, others may simply require a concise report summarising the results. By recognizing and accommodating these diverse preferences, you can ensure that the results are shared in a manner that best aligns with each participant's unique needs and motivations.

Sharing results can extend beyond researchers and also involve citizens in meaningful ways. The act of sharing research results is no longer limited to researchers alone. By involving participants in sharing results, several advantages emerge, including the ability to reach wider audiences and resonate with different segments of society. Notably, participants with influential social media channels or artistic skills can contribute in unique ways, amplifying the reach and impact of the shared results. Building upon this notion, the [SOCIO-BEE project](#) has taken a proactive approach by providing a range of tools and training to empower participants and equip them with the necessary confidence and skills to effectively communicate the outcomes of the project.

Managing delay between citizens' participation and results sharing

Managing delay between citizens' participation and results sharing means maintaining communication and engagement. There may be a time lag between citizens' participation in collecting data and the delivery of the research results. This delay poses a

challenge in maintaining engagement and a sense of ownership throughout the process. However, effective communication plays a vital role in bridging this gap. In the [European Citizen Science project](#), they provided a summary of co-creation workshops and updates to participants who were unable to participate ensures that everyone remains involved and informed.

Creative tools

Embracing creative approaches to maximise result sharing. Incorporating creative approaches can significantly enhance the dissemination of research results, even when working with limited financial resources. [Surfing for Science](#) utilises [Instagram](#) as a channel to showcase captivating images from the laboratory and share scientific data. Additionally, they leverage the production of t-shirts featuring results from samples, turning individuals who wear these shirts into "walking disseminators". Another example is the [Sensing for Justice project](#), which produced a [graphic novel](#) that effectively conveys the research outcomes while minimising potential political sensitivities. To further expand their reach, they have now introduced a theatre play. Blogs offer yet another avenue for sharing research results. The [COESO project](#), for instance, leverages the power of blogging by providing each pilot with a dedicated blog to document the research process. Participants often contribute to writing blog posts. [Hypotheses](#), a platform dedicated to humanities and social sciences research blogs, serves as a valuable resource for hosting these blogs.

Connecting with schools and science outreach activities

Connecting with schools and science outreach activities organised by universities or municipalities can enhance result sharing. The [School of Ants](#) project engaged several primary schools, an opportunity for teachers to involve pupils in creating graphs and other ways of playing with the data, where sharing results becomes a learning experience. Drawing from past experiences, the [Citizen Science Contact Point at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel](#) emphasises the significance of presenting outcomes from citizen science projects in various informal settings, including festivals and local events organised by the city or regional governments.

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Citizen science and the law: potential applications

Anna Berti Suman

October 2023

Image credits: Andrea Marinelli, Photographer for SensJus

Environment and the law

Civic environmental monitoring can offer valuable evidence for environmental law enforcement, both in judicial arenas and in alternative dispute resolution e.g., through mediation techniques. The legal potential and implications of civic environmental monitoring are the main focus of the project [Sensing for Justice](#) (funded by a MSCA Individual Fellowship and by the Dutch Research Council).

The project indeed explores how civic environmental monitoring can offer valuable evidence for environmental law enforcement, both in judicial arenas and in alternative dispute resolution e.g., through mediation techniques. It also addresses an urgent need to understand emerging possibilities of the practice, starting from the actual demands and questions of people affected by environmental issues.

To bring ordinary people closer to the law and to courts, the **Sensing for Justice** project goes where the people are, through engaged ethnography;

identifies which barriers need to be removed for civic evidence to be used for law enforcement, performing legal review and advocacy work in fora such as Meeting of the Parties to the Aarhus Convention, to support the right of every person to contribute environmental information. The project also uses art to translate complex legal concepts to ordinary people through images and examples, and generate empathy. Results are brought to public spaces such as squares, schools and libraries to stimulate further awareness.

These topics and more concrete legal questions were discussed during the workshop on Legal challenges in citizen science – held on August 1st, 2023, as part of the ECS Collaboration Group. (See also the article by Annelies Duerinckx, [Legal challenges for citizen science initiatives: stories from the field](#))

Real-world scenarios

To explore and reflect together on the opportunity that the law offered or could offer to our initiatives, we engaged in an exercise of imagining two real-world scenarios. The proposed tasks were two, and the one the opposite of the other: on the one hand the task was to make laws in favour of citizen science, on the other hand the task was to make law to hamper it. The two groups received the below instructions:

In favour of citizen science

Making law(s) favouring citizen science came up with a number of points, the most remarkable being the need to set up legal advice spaces at national and local levels for citizens; in addition at the European level and national and local levels there should be (more) legal activity to give legitimacy to citizen science initiatives and offer them clear legal guidance in which to operate.

Against citizen science

Making law(s) against citizen science relates to the tensions between private property and the common good (supporting the need to perform citizen science) and freedom of information. Special categories of data – like health data – need specific cautions and require a mandatory Data

Management Plan and an Ethical Impact Assessment. In case a private company is involved in an issue, to ensure information balance, the concerned company should have the right to respond to the civic data with their own data.

Science plays a crucial role and has a massive impact on our lives and well being. Scientific and technological aspects, ethical issues, social and economical factors are all intertwined to create a complex texture connected by delicate bonds. The law is a further dimension in it. Together, we can make it a tool to protect and foster the role citizens can have in taking decisions and shaping our present and our future.

CALL TO ACTION

Lastly, we discussed that there is not an ECSA working group on this topic. There is a WG focusing on how citizen science is influencing policy (and vice versa), whereas there is not one WG exploring how the law influences citizen science (and vice versa). We are exploring interest from the ECS community to join a new ECSA working group on Citizen Science & the Law. Interested? Flag it to Anna Berti Suman, anna.bertisuman@gmail.com and Annelies Duerinckx, annelies@scivil.be.

The [ECSA Conference 2024](#) can also be a good occasion for an informal discussion around this matter.

Further readings

On the intersection between citizen science and the legal framework in Europe: Berti Suman, A., Balestrini, M., Haklay, M. and Schade, S., 2023. When Concerned People Produce Environmental Information: A Need to Re-Think Existing Legal Frameworks and Governance Models?. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 8(1), p.10. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.496>

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On the criminalization of citizen science occurred in the US:
<https://blog.ucsusa.org/science-blogger/did-wyoming-really-just-outlaw-citizen-science-735/>

Legal challenges for citizen science initiatives: stories from the field

Annelies Duerinckx

October 2023

Image credits: Simona Cerrato

What are the legal hurdles faced by citizen science projects? This is a particularly challenging topic and there is an urgent need for clearer guidance. This is what we try to do at Scivil, the Flemish citizen science centre in Belgium, among other actions to support citizen science initiatives.

Navigating rules on volunteering

"I receive a sickness allowance. Do I need permission from the health insurance fund to plant soy in my garden for science?"

One legal question is whether citizen science qualifies as volunteering, particularly for individuals receiving benefits such as retirement, sickness, or unemployment allowances. In some cases, citizens may need permission from relevant authorities to participate in citizen science activities. For instance, if you receive a sickness allowance, you may need approval from your health insurance fund before engaging in citizen science. In some cases, this makes perfect sense, such as when you plan to spend a large part of your days delving into the archives of the local history museum doing research. In other cases, the blurred line between volunteering and citizen science can

lead to confusion. It feels strange to require permission from your health insurance fund to put an air quality sensor on your house.

The rules governing volunteering are designed to protect volunteers and to ensure they are not held liable for potential damages. When a citizen science project takes place within your own home, the liability risk is minimal, and permission may not be required. Still, it is up to the citizen to verify this. When the project extends beyond your home or involves more significant risks, project organisers should provide insurance coverage for their citizen scientists.

The challenge lies in determining when citizen science crosses the threshold from casual volunteering into a more structured project. For instance, counting butterflies in your garden might not trigger the same requirements as participating in a lab-based scientific endeavour.

Privacy proof citizen science

"We want to record noises in a city environment to train a smart system to automatically recognise the type of sound. What are the privacy rules for this?"

Privacy considerations are a significant aspect of citizen science. For example, recording human sound can be legally complex. Recording human conversation falls under criminal law and often requires permission from legal authorities such as an investigating judge. Another example are citizen science projects involving citizens' location data. For instance, mapping the safety of students' routes to school is a valuable endeavour. However, it's crucial to safeguard students' privacy by not revealing their starting points (i.e., their homes).

To address these challenges, citizen science initiatives must establish privacy-proof protocols. For human sound recordings, the project can opt for very brief snippets that avoid capturing meaningful conversations, though this may limit the data's usefulness for training AI systems, which requires substantial, meaningful datasets. When mapping students' school routes, excluding the first kilometre to protect their identity and home location could be an option. However, this may not suffice for those in less populated regions. Conversely, it could prove too extensive for

students residing very close to school, hindering their participation in the project altogether.

Finding a privacy-proof protocol that accommodates all potential citizen scientists can be a complex task. Balancing the collection of valuable data with privacy protection is an ongoing challenge in citizen science projects.

Intellectual property rights

"As a citizen, if my idea for a new AI application gets picked by the citizen science project, what are my patenting and commercialization rights?"

Intellectual property rights in citizen science are complex and involve questions of ownership, recognition, and commercialization. When a citizen scientist's idea is incorporated into a project, it raises issues regarding who owns the resulting intellectual property. Recognition and credit for citizen scientists are also important considerations. Some projects are addressing this with clear policies on ownership, attribution, and procedures for handling commercial opportunities. Still, these matters often require negotiation and legal expertise, areas where citizens typically do not possess specialised knowledge.

Supporting citizen science initiatives

In light of these legal challenges, the participants of the workshop on *Citizen science & the Law: potential applications* - moderated by Anna Berti Suman (Sensing for Justice project) and Annelies Duerinckx (Scivil) and held on August 1st, 2023, as part of the ECS Collaboration Group - discussed the need for support for citizen science initiatives in navigating legal aspects. There was consensus that citizen science initiatives need to be made aware of existing laws they can leverage or must adhere to.

One proposed idea that received a lot of support is to establish legal points of contact for citizen science initiatives, similar to those available for tenants seeking legal advice. While fostering such legal support points on a European level would be beneficial, it is essential to integrate them locally. These support points should offer tailored legal advice aligned with the specific rules and regulations of individual countries. Such an

approach ensures that citizen science projects receive the precise guidance needed to address their unique legal challenges effectively.

In conclusion, while citizen science offers a powerful means of engaging the public in scientific research, it is not without legal challenges. To overcome these challenges, there is a need for guidelines, solutions, and increased awareness among citizen science organisers.

Citizen engagement, motivation and recruitment

Antonio Filograna, Meritxell Martell and Florence Gignac

December 2023

Image credits: Ars Electronica, Linz, Austria (Ph. Simona Cerrato)

Citizen scientists are undoubtedly the vital essence of any citizen science project. Therefore, keeping an eye on what interests and motivates the citizens, and what they expect from their involvement in the project, is crucial to ensure not only the success but also the sustained longevity of citizen science initiatives. Yet, maintaining consistent engagement and ensuring citizens remain highly motivated throughout can pose a challenge for many citizen science initiatives. On October 7th, Antonio Filograna from [DECIDO](#) and Meritxell Martell from [RadoNorm](#) organised a session, discussing strategies on how to engage citizens and, most importantly, keep them involved and motivated. This sparked some really interesting discussions and gave us some takeaways to think about.

There is no single set of most effective engagement tools and strategies, but those that are tailored to specific groups and leverage networks and communities prove to be powerful.

Before strategizing on how to engage citizens in a project, it is important to understand the type of participants you want to involve, as well as to be aware of their needs, motivations, and potential barriers to participation. In that case, a stakeholder mapping is always a good first step. Tools and strategies will highly depend on the target groups you aim to engage, which can range from announcements on TV shows and national news to newspapers, radio podcasts, social media campaigns, flyers, email invitations, etc. One strategy often overlooked is the power of the

snowballing effect or word of mouth, which stands as an effective engagement strategy according to several members of the ECS Collaboration Group. This can be achieved by tapping into established community networks such as civil society organisations or local associations, attending their events and fostering collaborations. In RadoNorm, local libraries, local health authorities, word of mouth and the social media of local authorities have been crucial to recruit citizen scientists. Some groups have representatives and gatekeepers and their support can be harnessed and beneficial in spreading the word about the project. In the DECIDO project, a strategy to engage citizens was the Social Hackathon. This is nothing technical but, following the example of a hackathon, it involves various participants such as citizen organisations, businesses, NGOs, and policy makers who gathered together to brainstorm, analyse data, and ultimately find potential solutions to a problem, using the motto “*Learn, discuss and then decide*”. It is also important to note that the selection of engagement tools and strategies will significantly depend on the inclusivity objectives and ambitions you wish to address in your citizen science activities.

Yes, motivations for participation are very diverse - but overall, fun must be present!

After learning about projects from the ECS Collaboration Group, it is evident how motivations can significantly vary from one citizen to another and from one cultural context to another, even within a single project. Sometimes it is the desire to be part of something; other times, it is for personal reasons, such as acquiring new skills, or to enact change and contribute to evidence-based policymaking. Also, some seek to be recognized as equal stakeholders in policy changes. But ultimately, fun is a critical element in establishing and maintaining motivation. Participation should be enjoyable, especially considering that citizen scientists contribute during their leisure time without financial compensation. In this context, the adoption of a “gaming paradigm” fosters a sense of excitement among citizens, making their involvement more appealing and accessible. It transforms an otherwise daunting process into an enjoyable experience, attracting a wider range of citizens to actively participate.

Citizen scientists dropouts are entirely normal and should serve as a catalyst for researchers to self-reflect on the reasons why participants disengage.

Some level of dropout is natural in all projects. Instead of viewing this negatively, it can serve as an indicator of areas where the project may be lacking. There are different reasons for citizens to drop out. For instance, dropout rates can rise when citizen scientists lack trust or confidence in the project's activities and their potential impact. This can be attributed to the fact that citizens may not directly witness the results or outcomes of their contributions. This may indicate a lack of transparency in the project. To mitigate this, it is thus crucial to clearly communicate what the project aims to achieve in each of its steps, as well as its limitations, especially when unexpected changes occur. Ensuring that citizens are well-informed about what they are accomplishing is also very important.

Engagement is an ongoing effort and therefore, delegating efforts and adopting an adaptive approach to engagement strategies are key.

Engaging citizens extends beyond a single moment, such as the recruitment phase, and it requires researchers to sustain efforts to keep project activities relevant until the end. While juggling various roles, researchers need to be pragmatic and strategically plan their involvement with citizen scientists. Ensuring that a designated person is responsible for maintaining transparency and communication is important and this can be done by considering incorporating facilitation experts or dedicating an individual exclusively to engagement efforts. Above all, adopting an adaptive approach throughout the project in terms of engaging citizens, which continually aligns with evolving or changing motivations, is paramount. In fact, engagement might need to be tailored to the specific lifeworlds and life stages people are in. This can influence their preferred and possible ways of participating in the project.